

EFL classroom, petri dish, panopticon, and free world: How do they merge through action research?

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Action research is a promising and significant research methodology that paves the way for intervention, development and change not only within small groups and communities of practice but also within larger societies. Building on a terse-and-informative description of the four major action research theories (Action Science, Cooperative Inquiry, Participatory Action Research, and Living Educational Theory), this paper argues that EFL classes are essentially micro societies where language socialization takes place; it is argued further that the micro society of the EFL classroom can be (a) a ‘garbage in garbage out’ petri dish at the service of mechanical imparting of linguistic competence to students, (b) a Foucauldian ‘panopticon’ put to ideological use by a despot ruling an oppressed society, or (c) a free milieu aspiring after human development and social change. The paper concludes that action research might be redefined as aristocrat/elitist just-in-case research reformulated as just-in-time change-and-development-oriented ongoing ‘process’ research involving participants/informants as co-researchers or sources of (social) action, but not simply data mines or sources of information.

Keywords: Action Science; Collaborative Inquiry; Cooperative Inquiry; EFL Classroom; Foucault; Free World; Living Educational Theory; LET; Panopticon; Participatory Action Research; Petri Dish

1. Introduction

When Lewin (1946) coined the term ‘action research’, it was meant as a just-in-case tool developed to be used in social sciences, a tool not only for researching social action—mainly pertaining to minority groups—but also for bringing about transformative social changes while engaging (a) action, (b) research, and (c) reflection simultaneously. In his wildest dreams, though, Lewin would perhaps never imagine that his philosophical-methodological tool might someday turn into a research-informed approach to class instruction at teachers’ disposal. Due to its potentials, though, action research has been put to use as a rigorous research tool in classroom settings in schools and universities around the world, added that EFL professionals have seen its

'affordance', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), as a potential approach to formal language teaching and research.

In this paper, I will first present a short overview of the origins and developments of action research. I will then discuss its four major theories. This will be followed by a discussion of how it can be used in EFL contexts with the aim of promoting social change and human development.

2. Background

Action research, à la Lewin (1946, 1958), consists of a 'spiral' of steps, and each step, in turn, is a circle/process that comprises (a) planning, (b) action, and (c) evaluation. Actions are taken to solve problems, and research is undertaken to (a) find the underlying causes of action, (b) make predictions for future, and (c) evaluate personal and/or group changes. As such, action research comprises (a) action, (b) research, and (c) reflection.

Criticizing traditional top-down approaches to the study of social phenomena, Lewin (1958) argued in favor of a new approach that would aspire after gaining knowledge 'through' action and then using that knowledge 'for' action. As such, action research is tantamount to knowledge 'through' and 'for' action. Action research is, therefore, a problem-based inquiry that is performed by practitioners, and their own practices are the subject matter of action research (McNiff & Whitehead, 2005).

As a modern method of inquiry, action research has flourished in the past few decades, and it is now a major force in social sciences; since its advent by Lewin (1946), it has theoretically been approached from different perspectives. Some of the most influential approaches to action research include:

- Action Science (Argyris, 1970, 1980, 1994)
- Cooperative Inquiry (Heron, 1971, 1996; Reason & Bradbury, 2001; Reason & Rowan, 1981)
- Participatory Action Research (Freire, 1970)
- Living Educational Theory (Barry, 2012a, 2012b)

2.1. Action science (AS)

The first gamer in town is Action Science (AS). Human beings, when trapped in difficult situations, have their ways of tackling those situations. The question of 'how they design their actions' lies at the heart of Argyris' (1970, 1980, 1994) approach to action research. Argyris noted that human actions in such situations are (a) aimed at achieving intended desirable results and (b) bound by certain environmental and social/contextual variables. Seen in this light, action research is distinguished from traditional empirical research in that the

latter would opt for 'controlling' environmental variables and studying cause-effect relationships in isolated environments. Action research, however, assumes that environmental variables should not be controlled; rather, they should be part and parcel of the research process. Argyris (1970, 1980, 1994) suggested that action research can incorporate governing variables—be they environmental or social/contextual—into the action process through either (a) single-loop learning or (b) double-loop learning. A single-loop learning cycle designs actions in such a way as to (a) achieve intended desirable outcomes and simultaneously (b) suppress all conflicts about environmental and social/contextual variables that govern those actions. By way of contrast, a double-loop learning cycle does not suppress those conflicts; rather, it openly inquires about those conflicts and tries to transform them in the action-plan process in such a way as to make them facilitate the achievement of intended desirable outcomes (Argyris, 1970, 1980, 1994).

2.2. Cooperative inquiry (CI)

Cooperative/collaborative Inquiry (CI), the second gamer in town, assumes that research should be performed 'with' people, but not 'on' them (Heron, 1971). Being a with-but-not-on people methodology, CI is an all-inclusive research plan that actively involves all parties (e.g., co-researchers, participants, and so forth) in a collaborative research process. The research cycle that cooperative inquiry dwells on encompasses four types of knowledge; (a) propositional, (b) practical, (c) experiential, and (d) presentational. Propositional knowledge refers to the totality of the existing knowledge on a topic or in a contemporary field of science. Practical knowledge is that type of knowledge which emerges through hands-on experimentation. 'Experiential knowledge' refers to any real-time feedback that can be obtained through interaction with the outside world. Finally, presentational knowledge is the crafting of new practices through involvement in various processes of artistic rehearsal (Boud et al., 1985; Heron, 1985, 1992).

What CI essentially does is to create a research cycle among all of these types of knowledge. The cycle consists of four stages, and in each cycle, two things happen: (a) the knowledge of the proposition introduced in the previous stage is deepened, and (b) a new proposition is introduced and new knowledge on/about it is gathered (Heron, 1996; Reason, 1995; Reason & Bradbury, 2001; Reason & Rowan, 1981). In the first stage—a reflection phase—decision is made about the best methods and topics of inquiry; as such, this stage draws on propositional knowing. In the second stage, the first action plan is put to practice within the group and (a) the agreed action is tested, (b) outcomes from the testing are recorded, and (c) conformity between the emerging ideas from stage one and the actions is evaluated; as such, this stage engages practical knowing (cf. Boud et al., 1985; Heron, 1985, 1992). In the third stage, another

action phase is introduced with the aim of generating new and deeper feelings and awareness through one's inquiries and experiences. In this stage, individuals from the group engage in actions outside of the group—i.e., in their routine life courses—to explore the probable consequences of their inquiries and actions. This phase may afford new insights, actions, and fields that might depart from the ideas initially introduced in previous phases; this phase engages experiential knowledge. Finally, stage four in CI is a second reflection phase in which co-researchers engage in reflecting upon their experiences as well as the data they collected in previous stages. This phase is essentially an adjustment phase in which (a) original ideas from previous phases might be re-framed and, at the same time, (b) inquiry procedures might be amended. Involving presentational knowledge, this stage is where co-researchers decide if additional cycles are needed (Heron, 1996; Reason, 1995; Reason & Bradbury, 2001; Reason & Rowan, 1981).

2.3. Participatory action research (PAR)

Participatory Action Research (PAR) is the third gamer in town. PAR has mainly to do with education, but it can also be applied to other fields of human development/inquiry. It is based on the notion of critical pedagogy (Daftarifard & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011; Freire, 1970; Sánchez & Chapetón, 2021), which assumes that students should no longer be seen as passive receivers of knowledge from their teachers. PAR is essentially a perspective on action research that persuades members of the communities that are affected by it to take part in the research process as active participants (Freire, 1982; Hall, 1975, 2005; Whyte, 1991). Put in a nutshell, PAR assumes that the optimal way to understand the world is through a collaborative action-and-reflection process that aims at changing the world. As such, it would not be wrong if we emphasized that collective inquiry is part and parcel of PAR—where social history works in tandem with experience to inform any form of experimentation. According to Reason and Bradbury (2008), both inquiry and action are brought by all co-researchers (i.e., members of a community engaging in PAR) to bear on any issue that they find significant. As such, PAR differs from mainstream methods of inquiry that build on certain taken-for-granted principles including, among others, (a) statistical analyses, (b) controlled experimentation, and (c) reproducibility of methods and findings (Reason & Bradbury, 2008). Co-researchers engaging in PAR are active driven-by-free-will participants who bring the 'affordances', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), of history and experience to grow knowledge and make their own thoughts sound—added that they do so through concerted collective and collaborative (a) action, (b) effort, and (c) self-investigation (cf. Chevalier & Buckles, 2013).

Unlike traditional mainstream research methods (e.g., empirical, descriptive, correlational, etc.) each of which is a monolithic set of pre-defined principles (i.e., a static 'a priori' product), PAR does not boil down into a monolithic pre-defined method of inquiry; rather, it is a dynamic process of inquiry in the sense that its different theories and practices are developed through pluralistic perspectives on (a) the processes of inquiry (e.g., evidence-driven reasoning, critical learning, collaborative fact-finding, collective self-experimentation, etc.) and (b) the development of human knowledge (Allen, 2001; Chambers, 2008). Collective human agency armed with lessons learnt from social history is the main drive behind PAR that enables it to develop knowledge through co-researchers' collaborative action aimed at transforming and advancing the world. Research that does not result in the advancement of human conditions, society, and environment has no place in PAR (I will return to this in section 4 below); as such, it would not be wrong if I used the term 'aesthetic research' (or 'aristocrat/elitist research') to refer to traditional approaches to scientific inquiry which embark on research simply for the sake of 'scientism' (i.e., collecting and preserving knowledge, but waiting for social 'change' or human 'development' to happen by itself). In other words, PAR incorporates 'community action' into traditional approaches to research, so it would probably be more precise if we called it 'change-oriented research' or 'agency-driven research'. It should also be noted that PAR is not tantamount to cooperative inquiry (CI)—the second gamer in town—in the sense that PAR sees all community members as co-researchers whereas CI, at best, sees them as informants.

2.4. Living educational theory (LET)

The fourth gamer in town is living educational theory (LET). At the heart of William Barry's (2012a) conception of living educational theory (LET) lies the existential notion of 'ontological weight' (cf. Marcel, 1963). In much the same way as an Eleatic philosopher would ask questions about the reality, essence, quality, or weight of his/her own existence, an action researcher, seen through the LET prism, is one who aspires after knowing 'how he/she can improve what he/she is doing'.

As such, LET defines action research as a 'living practice' (Carson & Sumara, 1997). Very often, a LET researcher is ontologically tantamount to a 'living contradiction' in his/her professional practice, one that thinks one way, but may act in another. A LET researcher is one who has certain personal beliefs and values which may differ from the norms that permeate all aspects of the community or workplace in which he/she lives or works, yet he/she conducts research to develop an educational theory that (a) does enable people to enhance their learning outcomes and achievement, and (b) can be evaluated in terms of the reform it brings about, the growth it spurs, etc. As such, LET is not

only a form of action research but also a type of living practice (Carson & Sumara, 1997).

The investigation that a LET researcher conducts not only is shaped by him/her but also shapes him/her. The motif lying at the heart of LET, à la Carson and Sumara (1997), is not how a LET researcher might generate a living legacy for himself/herself through an ‘I-It’ theory approach toward knowledge and other forms of life; rather, it is the principle question of how the LET researcher might live a life that would also include the practice of (educational) action research (Carson & Sumara, 1997). This motif is exactly what (a) gives LET its ontological weight, and (b) removes the border between ‘theory’ and ‘practice’ whereby making the LET researcher honest about, and aware of, the biases that permeate his/her existential, spiritual, and emotional identities (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2013; for more on ‘identity’, see Susilowati, 2020; Guzzo & Gallo, 2019; Haggström, 2020; Herat, 2020). Seen through this prism, LET is essentially a meaningful way of life augmented by life-affirming-and-life-enhancing as well as need-fulfilling-and-performance-enhancing values and practices (Barry, 2012a; Whitehead, 2018; Whitehead & McNiff, 2006). As such, a LET researcher does not see ‘doing research’ as one of his/her roles or identities (a professional identity, if you will), but as part of his/her ‘self’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2013).

3. Action research at school

All in all, the four gamers in town described above have developed their perspectives on action research on the basis of the assumption that ‘inadequacy’ results in the realization of the ‘need for change’ which, in turn, may motivate ‘action’. As such, action research—with its three circles of (a) planning, (b) action, and (c) fact-finding about the consequences of action (or unfreezing, changing, and refreezing)—is essentially an ‘adaptation’ process, à la Piaget (1972; see also Gruber & Voneche, 1977), that requires the interplay of ‘assimilation’ and ‘accommodation’ mechanisms.

It all starts with the realization of a disconfirmation or dilemma which brings a ‘need for change’ to the fore; this realization is what can be called the ‘unfreezing’ phase in which the individual or the group opts out of the existing order of things—or sets out to ‘shift’ the domineering ‘paradigm’, à la Kuhn (1962). ‘Unfreezing’ is then followed by a ‘changing’ phase in which (a) the existing situation is evaluated and (b) new practices and models are tested and explored. This phase, in turn, is followed by a ‘refreezing’ phase in which an adequate model of behavior is adopted and reinforced; the newly-adopted model can remain in place until a newer need for change is felt and a newer action cycle begins. Action research has, therefore, a ‘spiral’ nature.

It should be noted that traditional mainstream approaches to research—be they qualitative or quantitative (cf. Mason et al., 1991)—differ from action research, which is essentially a ‘plan’ for action. Traditional mainstream research forms might roughly be called large-scale ‘reflection on action’, but action research can eloquently be termed ‘reflection in action’—and it does not need to be large-scale (cf. Farrell, 2015; Salmani Nodoushan, 2011; Schön, 1987).

As for action research at school, teachers (i.e., the ‘de facto’ action researchers) should not think that performing ‘reflection in action’ is going to be an extra burden in their regular regimen (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009a). In classroom settings, action research, à la Slavin, (2006), is a form of research that is conducted to improve teaching and learning (cf. Ross-Fisher, 2008), the results of which can then be shared in faculty meetings as well as in-service workshops or on school websites. As such, action research is a powerful tool at teachers’ disposal the implementation of which might secure professional development and enhanced educational outcomes. Teachers can take seven consecutive steps to implement action research as a teaching tool:

- (1) Identify and define the problem;
- (2) Frame the research question(s);
- (3) Review the related literature;
- (4) Collect the data;
- (5) Analyze the data, answer the question(s), and draw conclusions;
- (6) Draft a plan of action for the future and reflect on the experience; and
- (7) Share what has been learned with colleagues.

Identification of a problem in a classroom or a school is an easy task; teachers do not need to go a far way to find problems (Sagor, 2000). Proofreading students’ compositions, for instance, can afford a rich repertoire of textual features (cf. Hernandez, 2022, 2023) and errors and goofs (cf. Ananda et al., 2020; Pichette & Lesniewska, 2018; Salmani Nodoushan, 2007a,b, 2009a, 2016, 2018; Yusuf et al., 2021), which the teacher can collect as his/her data for an action research. Students’ compositions are not the only places where teachers can search for problems; in a broader sense, they may search for other issues such as poor class attendance, bullying or aggressive behavior on the playground, content-area assessments (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2020, 2021c,d), lack of parental involvement, poor performance on specific tests or subtests, an entire grade level that scores below expectations, or language skills that do not meet grade-level expectations (cf. Ross-Fisher, 2008). Once a problem is identified, the teacher can ask the following questions: Is this problem prevalent enough to deserve an action-research plan? How can I decide if the observed problem is a real issue in dire need of immediate action, and not just a simple concern? Is my belief based on tangible evidence?

Once the teacher decides that the selected problem is worth an action research plan, relevant research questions(s) can be framed. This is the second step in the action research process. Framing research questions requires that the teacher use precise 'wording' so that the questions will be 'narrow, clear, specific, and researchable' (Ross-Fisher, 2008; Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b). A clearly-worded research question, à la Ross-Fisher (2008), is one that includes three elements: (a) the student population, (b) the desired result, and (c) the specific strategy for achieving that result (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b). An example of a clearly-worded question that includes these elements might be: Does the use of learning strategies improve my less-proficient medical students' reading comprehension scores? (cf. Nemati et al., 2010). This question is a good one because (a) it includes the three elements described above, and (b) is only answerable if the teacher actually implements a specific strategy, technique, or intervention (i.e., learning strategies) intended to elicit a change (i.e., improved reading comprehension scores) in his classroom. Ross-Fisher (2008) used the term 'planning action research questions' to refer to the process of writing appropriate research questions; this process includes two steps: (a) drafting the elements—listed above—that need to be present in the wording of the questions, and (b) writing the question on the basis of that draft. The first step, in turn, requires that the teacher (a) identify the specific student population, (b) decide what the desired end result should be, (c) determine what the best method for achieving the desired end result might be, and (d) decide how the question could possibly be answered (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b).

In the third step, the teacher will then review the related literature on the topic of his/her research (cf. Pyrczak, 1999) and will simultaneously avoid redundancy. The preferred rhetorical organization for the literature review is from general to specific. By the end of the literature review, the researcher/teacher should have clearly stated what previous authoritative researchers have written on the topic (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b). The literature review should also function as a pedestal for the action research in the sense that it should provide support for its specific research design. This will ascertain that the action-research project shows some promise for success (Ross-Fisher, 2008).

After writing up the action research question, the teacher can then collect the data that will answer it. Being the fourth step in the action research process, data collection is bound by a specific research 'methodology' (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b), and it is because of this that some action researchers prefer to use the term 'methodology' for this phase of action research—instead of data collection. According to Salvia and Ysseldyke (2001), this step in the action research process must align with action research questions and must also decide (a) what data must be collected, (b) how they must be collected,

and (c) how they must be analyzed. Unlike traditional mainstream research types (be they qualitative or quantitative) that require large sample sizes and complex statistical analyses (cf. Patten, 2000, 2001), action research can even be conducted with only one student (like in case studies); as such, methodology in action research is quite simple, even much simpler than traditional qualitative research designs that work with population mean, median, and mode and engage interviews, questionnaires, observations, portfolios, etc. in data collection (Pyrzczak, 1999). In fact, methodology in action research resorts to (a) teacher observation, (b) examination of student work samples, (c) interest inventories, (d) students' performance on teacher-made tests, or (e) students' performance on commercially-produced instruments—as sources of data (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b). Action-research data analysis, too, is much simpler than traditional mainstream research designs; the teacher can use (a) specific types of coding, (b) criterion-referenced scoring guides, or (c) certain rubrics—e.g., 'Rubrics for Success' (Ross-Fisher, 2005; Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b). Establishing a timeframe is the last consideration in action research methodology; it enables the teacher to remain focused and organized (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b).

The fifth step in the action research process is a macro step comprising three micro steps: (a) analyzing the collected data, (b) answering the question, and (c) drawing conclusions. According to Strauss and Corbin (1990), a commonly used procedure for data analysis in action research is to use (a) criterion-referenced rubrics or (b) pre-defined rating scales; nevertheless, teachers may want to engage their own methods—e.g., observation checklists—in data analysis. This, of course, does not mean that formal large-scale data analysis methods (e.g., statistical inferencing) cannot or should not be used; they are simply not typical of action research (Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b). Instead of formal analytical methods, the teacher (i.e., the 'de facto' action researcher) often seeks to find patterns of evidence (i.e., trends) in the collected data; an example is Salmani Nodoushan (2018), who searched for errors in a corpus of students' writings. Finding patterns of evidence is a crucial undertaking in action research because the major aim of action research is 'washback' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c)—i.e., to improve teaching and learning. In other words, the action researcher needs to decide "whether and to what extent the intended result is occurring within the context of the specific strategies or techniques employed in the investigation" (Ross-Fisher, 2008, p. 163). One option is to compare pre- and post-assessment data that will show if classroom techniques had any notable impact on learning. All in all, the teacher must be able to answer his/her research question and draw conclusions from his/her action research; where the analysis of the data cannot accomplish these tasks, there has to be a flaw in the design of the study, and the teacher will have to re-

view his/her analysis procedures and study design (Pyrzczak & Bruce, 2003; Ross-Fisher, 2008; Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b).

In the sixth step, the teacher drafts a plan of action based on the conclusions obtained from step five. Here is where 'reflection' comes to the fore (cf. Sagor, 2000; Salmani Nodoushan, 2011). The action plan is essentially tantamount to 'remedial work' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c)—instructional or otherwise—that will bring about some improvement and also advance education. It may, for instance, result in (a) the modification of instructional strategies, (b) changes in the curriculum, or (c) the alteration of the sequence of teaching materials. All in all, the action plan boils down into a set of theoretical or practical implications that will have some positive 'washback', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), on education. In this phase, the teacher/researcher will also reflect on the action research he/she has just conducted to (a) find its downsides and upsides and (b) see if and what he/she would do differently if the action research were to be replicated; this is essentially a 'reflective' undertaking which may require the implementation of teacher diaries, journals, learning logs, and so forth (Salmani Nodoushan, 2006a,b, 2011).

As for the last step in the action research process, the teacher may decide to disseminate his/her findings—e.g., share them with colleagues. Since the basic job of action research is to bring about some change/development, the dissemination of its findings is an absolutely important undertaking. As stated earlier, action research is not an aristocratic/elitist activity performed as a pastime. Rather, it is a vital activity that aspires after some development in human societies, and schools are just one area where development is supposed to be an ever-lasting aspiration. Unlike mainstream research designs that long to get their findings published in reputable journals, action research does not have to wait for indexed venues; its findings can be disseminated in local venues such as (a) after-school faculty meetings, (b) workshops, (c) school repositories/bulletins, (d) local conferences, (e) peer discussion groups, or (f) mailing lists (Ross-Fisher, 2008; Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b).

4. Discussion

It was stated above (in section 2.3.) that research that does not result in the advancement of human conditions, society, and environment has no place in (participatory) action research. This means that, in its most basic form, action research aims at the betterment of larger societies (e.g., a tribe, a city, a nation, the whole world). Needless to say, classrooms in general, and EFL classrooms in specific, are part and parcel of larger societies, and action-research oriented on (EFL) classrooms can not only advance classroom/school communities (i.e., student groups, teachers, or administrative school staff) but also develop the larger society in which students belong as citizens.

It is by this token that ‘action teaching’ has been proposed as a professional term (cf. Lewin, 1946) to serve as the educational counterpart to society-oriented ‘action research’ (Pappas, 2019). Social science and social action are often integrated through large-scale action-research studies that address issues of (inter)national concern in a macro society—e.g., misogyny, racism, anti-Semitism, prejudice, stigmatization, violence, etc. By way of analogy, a classroom—or any other professional community of practice—can be considered a micro society where topics of ‘educational’ concern can be probed through small-scale action research directed towards the development of the micro society—which, at the end of the day, will also impact and develop the macro society.

Based on small-scale action research projects in EFL classes, texts promoting ‘action on social issues’ can be integrated into language teaching materials. In an EFL reading comprehension classroom, for example, students are given ‘intensive reading’ training which is then supplemented with extensive outside-of-the-class reading assignments. In my own reading classes, students read course books such as *Developing Reading Skills* (Markstein & Hirasawa, 1978); I also assigned at least three novels for their extensive reading on which I gave them quizzes during the semester. Based on the results of small-scale action research studies I had conducted, I was quite selective in choosing the ‘right’ materials that could impart, in addition to linguistic knowledge, certain human virtues to my students. This means that language teachers can select extensive and intensive reading materials in such a way as to make sure their reading will raise students’ awareness of significant topics of (inter)national concern—misogyny, justice, racism, prejudice, stigmatization, etc. This is how the micro society of the EFL classroom can be integrated into the macro society of the whole world.

In basic-level writing courses, too, a similar strategy can be employed; bachelor EFL students in Iran—and I guess also in other countries—have to pass at least four writing courses: (a) Grammar and Writing I, in which they learn how to form grammatically-sound sentences; (b) Grammar and Writing II, in which they learn how to combine sentences to produce compound and complex sentences; (c) Advanced Writing, in which they learn different types of enumerative and argumentative paragraphs, and (d) Essay Writing, in which they learn to write five-paragraph argumentative and enumerative essays. Instead of contrived lifeless sentences (e.g., Flying planes is dangerous.), the teacher may draw on his/her ‘creativity’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018a) to use intention-bearing genuine utterances (e.g., Mr. Capone is a nigger.) in his/her ‘Grammar and Writing I’ class. In fact, intention-bearing genuine utterances are tools that can be used to develop students’ awareness of issues of human concern—racism in the case of ‘Mr. Capone is a nigger’ (cf. Allan et al., 2016; for more on intention-bearing genuine utterances, see Salmani Nodoushan,

2021a, 2022). A similar strategy may be used in Grammar and Writing II classes; compound and complex sentences are essentially forms of discourse prewired with cohesion and/or coherence, so additional layers of meaning might be seen in them—compare ‘John and Jill married, and they had a baby’ with ‘John and Jill had a baby, and they married’. Here, the teacher can engage a right selection of utterances to develop his/her students’ critical awareness of tacit meanings (e.g., implicatures, presuppositions, entailments, inferences, etc.) and power-negotiating ideologies concealed in ‘metadiscursive space’ and between or behind text lines (cf. Battista, 2022; D’Avanzo, 2022; David et al., 2022; Lee, 2021; Padley, 2022; Raffone, 2022; Russo & Grasso, 2022; Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b; Wan, 2023; Zollo, 2022). Likewise, in Advanced Writing and Essay Writing courses, students are often supposed to go through five steps: (a) deduction, in which the internal structures of different kinds of paragraphs or essays are discussed; (b) exposure, in which students read at least a model paragraph or essay; (c) analysis, in which students gain greater understanding of the structure of the model paragraph or essay; (d) planning, in which students make outlines for their own paragraphs or essays based on their understanding of the models; and (e) writing, in which students write original full paragraphs or essays (Birjandi et al., 2004). Teachers can select the right model paragraphs or essays and give students the right topics to write on so that their awareness of more important issues (e.g., justice, environment, global warming, civic virtues, etc.) is developed through ‘cognitive coaching’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007b). This is how an ignored ‘affordance’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), of writing courses can be brought to bear on social change.

Likewise, bachelor EFL students have to pass four speaking course of which the first two focus on sound articulation, pronunciation, and prosody; the third and fourth courses, however, are conducted in the form of panel discussions on chosen topics. Here again, the teacher can engage in action research with the aim of choosing the discussion topics in such a way as to develop his/her students’ awareness of important issues (e.g., terrorism, liberty, peace, tolerance, etc.) of (inter)national concern. By the same token, many other EFL courses (e.g., Translation of Political Texts, Appraisal of Islamic Texts in Translation, etc.) have the ‘affordance’, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), to be engaged in social change and human development. Whether language teachers, specifically those living and working in countries ruled by demagogues, despots, or ‘clericatic mullaharchs’ have the guts or authorization to venture in that direction is a totally different story.

5. Conclusion

All in all, EFL classrooms—specifically at basic levels—are a rich-and-ready milieu in which language socialization finds occasion to take place (cf. Salmani

Nodoushan, 2021c). They are venues that have the 'affordance', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021c), to be put to many different uses. Their three major affordances include: (a) 'garbage in garbage out', or a contrived mechanical context in which frozen-and-mechanical forms of language are procedurally imparted to students who learn them through 'monkey-see-and-monkey-do' learning strategies such as audiolingual drilling; (b) ideologically-loaded Foucauldian 'panopticons' (Fontana-Giusti, 2013; Foucault, 1977), where the supposedly 'mindless' student is brain-washed through power-negotiating ideologies concealed in 'metadiscursive space' and between or behind text lines whereby he or she is disciplined and/or punished until he/she is finally hammered into the shape the 'despot' ruling the disciplinary society has so ordered; and (c) a free milieu, where both the teacher and the students bring their affordances, aspirations, and free will to bear on both language learning and social development.

In brief, Action research can be wielded in language classrooms to enhance students' whole person development which (a) will improve their hard and soft skills along with their linguistic competence, and (b) will enable them to lead and improve others. It can develop EFL students into people who know themselves, know how to improve themselves, know others, and know how to develop them. This is how EFL classroom action research can serve local societies and also the whole world. As a final remark, it can be concluded that action research might be redefined as aristocrat/elitist just-in-case research reformulated as just-in-time change-and-development-oriented ongoing 'process' research involving participants/informants as co-researchers or sources of (social) action, but not simply data mines or sources of information.

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References

Allan, K., Capone, A., & Kecskes, I. (2016). *Pragmemes and theories of language use*. Springer

- Allen, W. J. (2001). *Working together for environmental management: The role of information sharing and collaborative learning* [PhD Thesis]. Massey University.
- Ananda, R., Fitriani, S. S., & Samad, I. A. (2020). EFL teachers' perceptions on the causes of students' sentence errors. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 14(3), 99-118.
- Argyris, C. (1970). *Intervention: Theory and method*. Addison-Wesley.
- Argyris, C. (1980). *Inner contradictions of rigorous research*. Academic Press.
- Argyris, C. (1994). *Knowledge for action: A guide to overcoming barriers to organizational change*. Jossey-Bass.
- Barry, W. J. (2012a). *How can I improve my life-affirming, need-fulfilling, and performance enhancing capacity to understand and model the meaning of educational quality?* [PhD thesis]. Nottingham Trent University.
- Barry, W. J. (2012b). Is modern American education promoting a sane society? *International Journal of Science*, 2, 69-81.
- Battista, A. (2022). Donna Williams' *Nobody nowhere* and *Somebody somewhere*: A corpus-based discourse analysis of the author's language as a tool to negotiate one's relationship with the world and the self. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 95-116.
- Birjandi, P., Alavi, S. M., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2004). *Advanced writing*. Zabankadeh publications.
- Boud, D., Keogh, R., & Walker, D. (Eds.). (1985). *Reflection: Turning experience into learning*. Kogan Page.
- Breeze, R., & Azparren Legarre, M. P. (2021). Understanding change in practice: Identity and emotions in teacher training for content and language integrated learning (CLIL). *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(3), 25-44.
- Carson, T. R., & Sumara, D. J. (1997). *Action research as a living practice*. Peter Lang.
- Chambers, R. (2008). PRA, PLA and pluralism: Practice and theory. In P. Reason & H. Bradbury (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of action research: Participative inquiry and practice* (pp. 297-318). Sage.

- Chevalier, J. M., & Buckles, D. J. (2013). *Participatory action research: Theory and methods for engaged inquiry*. Routledge.
- D'Avanzo, S. (2022). Why hire disabled people? Corporate inclusive policies by three tech giants. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 137-156.
- Daftarifard, P., & Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). Globalized classroom, emancipatory competence, and critical pedagogy: A paradigm shift. In R. V. Nata (Ed.), *Progress in education* (pp. 147-162). Nova Science Publishers, Inc.
- David, M. K., Ali, A., & Shah, S. A. (2022). Investigating older persons' perceptions of ageist language and its use: Focus on Sindh, Pakistan. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 157-177.
- Farrell, P. (2015). Teacher-research and the art of the professional experiment: Reflective practice in the practical-knowledge tradition. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 9(1), 1-22.
- Fontana-Giusti, G. (2013). *Foucault for architects*. Routledge.
- Foucault, M. (1977). *Discipline and punishment: The birth of the prison* [trans. A. Sheridan]. Vintage Books.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Herder & Herder.
- Freire, P. (1982). Creating alternative research methods: Learning to do it by doing it. In B. Hall, A. Gillette & R. Tandon (Eds.), *Creating knowledge: A monopoly* (pp. 29-37). Society for Participatory Research in Asia.
- Gruber, H. E., & Voneche, J. J. (Eds.). (1977). *The essential Piaget*. Basic Books.
- Guzzo, S., & Gallo, A. (2019). "Please accept my apologies": English, food, and identity in TripAdvisor discourse. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 13(4), 141-158.
- Häggröm, M. (2020). The art of read-aloud, body language and identity construction: A multimodal interactional analysis of interaction between parent, child and picture book. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 14(1), 117-140.
- Hall, B. L. (1975). Participatory research: An approach for change. *Convergence*, 8(2), 24-32.

- Hall, B. L. (2005). In from the Cold: Reflections on participatory action research from 1970-2005. *Convergence*, 38(1), 5-24.
- Herat, M. (2020). Post-war letters to the Lord Mayor of Liverpool: Epistolary constructions of identity. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 14(2), 19-42.
- Hernandez, H. P. (2022). Prepositional phrases as noun postmodifiers in disciplinary research articles authored by Filipino researchers: A cross-examination. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(1), 21-44.
- Hernandez, H. P. (2023). Nouns as nominal premodifiers in disciplinary research articles written by Filipino research writers: A cross-investigation. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 17(1), 31-52.
- Heron, J. (1971). *Experience and method: An inquiry into the concept of experiential research*. University of Surrey.
- Heron, J. (1985). The role of reflection in co-operative inquiry. In D. Boud, R. Keogh & D. Walker (Eds.), *Reflection: Turning experience into learning* (pp. 128-138). Kogan Page.
- Heron, J. (1992). *Feeling and personhood: Psychology in another key*. Sage.
- Heron, J. (1996). *Cooperative inquiry: Research into the human condition*. Sage.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The structure of scientific revolutions*. University of Chicago Press.
- Lee, A. (2021). The protesters' demands: An analysis of (im)politeness of the Hong Kong Chief Executive in government press conferences. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(4), 79-106.
- Lewin, K. (1946). Action research and minority problems. *Journal of Social Issues*, 2(4), 34-46. doi:10.1111/j.1540-4560.1946.tb02295.x
- Lewin, K. (1958). *Group decision and social change*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Marcel, G. (1963). *Existential background of human dignity*. Harvard University Press.
- Markstein L., & Hirasawa, L. (1978). *Developing reading skills*. Newbury House Publishers. Inc.

- Mason, R. D., Lind, D. A., & Marchal, W. G. (1991). *Statistics: An introduction* (3rd ed.). Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
- McNiff, J., & Whitehead, J. (2005). *Action research: All you need to know*. Sage.
- Nemati, M., Salmani Nodoushan, M. A., & Ashrafzadeh, A. (2010). Learning strategies in proficient and less proficient readers in medicine. *Journal on Educational Psychology, 4*(2), 19-32.
- Padley, R. H. (2022). Shame, discrimination and disability: Unveiling narratives of obesity. *International Journal of Language Studies, 16*(4), 43-64.
- Pappas, S. (2019). *Changing the world from the classroom*. American Psychological Association. <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2019/11/classroom>
- Patten, M. L. (2000). *Understanding research methods: An overview of the essentials* (2nd ed.) Pyrczak Publishing.
- Patten, M. L. (2001). *Questionnaire research: A practical guide* (2nd ed.). Pyrczak Publishing.
- Piaget, J. (1972). *The psychology of intelligence*. Littlefield.
- Pichette, F., & Lesniewska, J. (2018). Percentage of L1-based errors in ESL: An update on Ellis (1985). *International Journal of Language Studies, 12*(2), 1-16.
- Pyrczak, F. (1999). *Evaluating research in academic journals*. Pyrczak Publishing.
- Pyrczak, F., & Bruce, R. R. (2003). *Writing empirical research reports: A basic guide for students of the social and behavioral sciences* (4th ed.). Pyrczak Publishing.
- Raffone, A. (2022). "Her leg didn't fully load in": A digitally-mediated social-semiotic critical discourse analysis of disability hate speech on TikTok. *International Journal of Language Studies, 16*(4), 17-42.
- Reason, P. (1995). *Participation in human inquiry*. Sage.
- Reason, P., & Bradbury, H. (Eds.). (2001). *Handbook of action research: Participative inquiry and practice*. Sage.

- Reason, P., & Bradbury, H. (Eds.). (2008). *The Sage handbook of action research: Participative inquiry and practice*. Sage.
- Reason, P., & Rowan, J. (1981). *Human inquiry: A sourcebook of new paradigm research*. John Wiley.
- Ross-Fisher, R. L. (2005). Developing effective success rubrics. *Kappa Delta Pi Record*, 41(3), 131-35.
- Ross-Fisher, R. L. (2008). Action research to improve teaching and learning. *Kappa Delta Pi Record*, 44(4), 160-164.
- Russo, K. E., & Grasso, A. (2022). Coping with dis/ableism in Twitter discourse: A corpus-based critical appraisal analysis of the Hidden Disabilities Sunflower Lanyard case. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(4), 65-94.
- Sagor, R. (2000). *Guiding school improvement with action research*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2006a). Language teaching: State of the art. *Asian EFL Journal*, 8(1), 169-193.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2006b). Research in the language classroom: State of the art. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 3(2), 63-72.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007a). Error treatment in the EFL writing class: Red pen method versus remedial instruction. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 4(3), 53-58.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2007b). Thinking on the write path. *Training Journal*, May 2007, 37-40.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009a). Identifying sources of bias in EFL writing assessment through multiple trait scoring. *The Modern Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 1(2), 28-53.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2009b). Improving learning and teaching through action research. *The Modern Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 1(4), 211-222.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2011). Reflective teaching in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes: An overview. *Journal on School Educational Technology*, 6(3), 1-6.

- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2013). The bilingual self or selves? *Annals Universitatis Apulensis - Series Philologica*, 14(2), 503-510.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2016). Working on the 'write' path: Improving EFL students' argumentative-writing performance through L1-mediated structural cognitive modification. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 10(4), 131-152.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018a). Implementation of the Beghetto-Kaufman-Baer approach to creativity and the four-c developmental trajectory in common core foreign language classrooms. In L. Caudle (Ed.), *Teachers and teaching: Practices, challenges and prospects* (pp. 157-174). Nova Science Publishers, Inc.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2018b). Toward a taxonomy of errors in Iranian EFL learners' basic-level writing. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 12(1), 101-116.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2020). Language assessment: Lessons learnt from the existing literature. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 14(2), 135-146.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021a). Demanding versus asking in Persian: Requestives as acts of verbal harassment. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(1), 27-46.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021b). Language and socialization? It is all about sociosemiotics. *Rivista Italiana di Filosofia del Linguaggio*, 15(2), 209-225. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4396/2021207>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021c). Test affordances or test function? Did we get Messick's message right? *International Journal of Language Studies*, 15(3), 127-140.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021d). Washback or backwash? Revisiting the status quo of washback and test impact in EFL contexts. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(3), 869-884. DOI: 10.24815/siele.v8i3.21406
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2022). Breaking out of the Gricean vicious cycle: Let's divorce semantics and just agree that there is no meaning in language. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 16(3), 33-60.
- Salvia, J., & Ysseldyke, J. E. (2001). *Assessment* (8th ed.) Houghton Mifflin.

- Sánchez, D. C., & Chapetón, C. M. (2021). Critical literacy in teacher education: Analyzing insights from EFL pre-service teachers in a Colombian public university. *International Journal of Language Studies, 15*(4), 1-28.
- Schön, D. (1987). *Educating the reflective practitioner*. Jossey-Bass higher education series.
- Slavin, R. E. (2006). *Educational psychology: Theory and practice* (8th ed.). Allyn & Bacon.
- Strauss, A. L., & Corbin, J. (1990). *Basics of qualitative research: Grounded theory procedures and techniques*. Sage Publications.
- Susilowati, M. (2020). When classroom interactions matter: Student identity (re)construction. *International Journal of Language Studies, 14*(3), 157-176.
- Wan, J. Y.-N. (2023). Structuring logical relations in workplace English telephone negotiation. *International Journal of Language Studies, 17*(1), 71-96.
- Whitehead, J. (2018). *Living theory research as a way of life*. Brown Dog Books.
- Whitehead, J., & McNiff, J. (2006). *Action research: Living theory*. Sage.
- Whyte, W. F. (Ed.). (1991). *Participatory action research*. Sage.
- Yusuf, Y. Q., Mustafa, F., & Iqbal, R. M. (2021). An inquiry into grammatical errors in writing committed by high achieving EFL students. *International Journal of Language Studies, 15*(2), 1-22.
- Zollo, S. A. (2022). Mental disabilities: Fighting stigma and discrimination in public service announcements. *International Journal of Language Studies, 16*(4), 117-136.